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Is Recycling Plastics to Protect Oceans an Illusion in the Face of Overproduction?

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The risk is that overly optimistic communication about the benefits of plastic recycling may delay consumer awareness, as people conform to the expected sorting behavior. Rich Carey/Shutterstock

Currently, only 10% of plastics are recycled, yet industries often present recycling as the ideal solution. However, this reasoning overlooks a crucial aspect: the production of plastic continues to grow, fueled by an increasing amount of virgin plastic, regardless of recycling rates. Global plastic production has doubled over the past fifteen years and shows no signs of slowing down.

Is plastic recycling as effective as it is touted to be? In 2024, the California prosecutor sued the oil company ExxonMobil¹, criticizing its communication about plastic recycling as misleading to the public and decision-makers. The California Department of Justice highlighted ExxonMobil's ²"clever marketing that promised recycling would solve the problem of the ever-increasing amount of plastic waste produced by the company."

This unprecedented lawsuit serves as a reminder, as the United Nations Ocean Conference (UNOC) begins on June 9th, that plastic recycling does not fulfill all the promises made by companies and waste managers. Indeed, 90% of the plastic produced annually is not recycled (Houssini et al., 2025).

The risk is that overly optimistic communication may delay consumer awareness, as people conform to expected sorting behaviors. However, the dangers of plastics are manifold. They impact the environment ³and human health ⁴throughout their value chain, whether they end up in oceans or soils due to water runoff.

Pollutant particles and substances are released into the environment at every stage of the plastic value chain: during oil extraction, plastic production, usage, and their management (or lack thereof) after use. This takes various forms, such as the wear and tear of paints, textiles, agricultural plastics⁵, and fishing nets.

The Limits of Recycling

The infrastructures for collecting, sorting, and recycling plastics require significant investment and operational expenses, sometimes for insufficient resources or recycled materials that are more expensive than virgin plastic produced from oil.⁶

Beyond the economic attractiveness of recycled plastic, recycling is also limited by the intrinsic properties of plastic materials. As recycling cycles multiply, the quality of the recycled raw material degrades (Alassali et al., 2021). This affects the final properties of recycled plastics and limits their applications. Indeed, more thorough upstream sorting is required, followed by the addition of more virgin raw materials and additives to remedy this and preserve the desired characteristics of the produced plastic.

Plastics produced and marketed thus have unequal recyclability properties. Currently, only thermoplastics are truly recyclable. Thermosetting plastics and elastomers are much more difficult to remelt at the end of their life.⁷

¹ <https://www.novethic.fr/environnement/biodiversite/exxonmobil-au-coeur-dun-proces-inedit-sur-la-pollution-plastique>

² <https://oag.ca.gov/news/press-releases/attorney-general-bonta-sues-exxonmobil-deceiving-public-recyclability-plastic>

³ <https://theconversation.com/pourquoi-les-dechets-plastiques-ne-se-degradent-ils-jamais-vraiment-252734>

⁴ <https://theconversation.com/des-produits-chimiques-dangereux-trouves-dans-des-plastiques-recycles-rendent-leur-utilisation-dangereuse-des-experts-expliquent-les-risques-221790>

⁵ <https://theconversation.com/peut-on-se-passer-de-plastique-en-agriculture-222839>

⁶ <https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/36963/POLSOL.pdf>

⁷ <https://infos.ademe.fr/magazine-juin-2023/dossier/les-grandes-familles-de-plastiques/>

Even for thermoplastics, the presence of chemical additives (such as plasticizers, stabilizers, colorants, or flame retardants⁸) limits the proportion of plastics that can be directed towards recycling.

These recycling difficulties are not trivial, as plastics threaten human and environmental health. There are approximately 16,000 chemical substances used for plastic production, a quarter of which are considered toxic to the environment or human health (Wagner et al., 2024). The risk of toxic substance accumulation increases with recycling due to the degradation or recombination of chemical substances and cross-contaminations that occur during the use, storage, sorting, and transport of plastics (Almroth et al., 2025).

Recycling or "Downcycling"?

Once plastic waste has been transformed into flakes or pellets, two possibilities for reintegrating recycled resins emerge, depending on the quality of the polymers and the contaminants present.

The first option is "closed-loop" recycling. Recycled materials are mixed with virgin materials to return to their original use⁶.

The second option is "open-loop" recycling (or downcycling). This concerns low-quality recycled resins, resulting from a mixture of different plastics. To reintegrate them into a plastic production chain, less demanding applications in terms of quality must be targeted.

The proportion of recycled plastic resins directed towards closed-loop recycling remains very limited. This is the case, for example, with clear PET (polyethylene terephthalate) water bottles. ⁹Almost all other plastic materials follow the downcycling path.

There is a third option, "energy recovery," either direct (by utilizing the energy released during incineration) or indirect (by producing fuels from plastics¹⁰). This is misleadingly qualified as recycling, as it does not involve remanufacturing material (Tangri, 2023).

Recycling Does Not Reduce Virgin Plastic Production

These infrastructures require significant investments to come to fruition, often justified by the argument that plastic recycling would reduce the need for virgin plastic. But is this really the case?

Let's start with a scenario based on the current trend, where plastic production includes about 10% recycled plastics and 90% virgin resins. By applying a constant recycling rate (10%) since the creation of the first recycling plants in 1973 (which is a high estimate, as the 10% proportion of recycled plastics was achieved later), we observe that the slope of the virgin plastic production curve (gray curve) remains very close to the historical curve ¹¹(solid black line) and future projections (black dashes).

⁸ <https://theconversation.com/pourquoi-les-retardateurs-de-flamme-dans-lair-leau-et-les-aliments-inquietent-237795>

⁹ <https://theconversation.com/dechets-plastiques-la-dangereuse-illusion-du-tout-recyclage-90359>

¹⁰ <https://theconversation.com/recyclage-et-valorisation-des-dechets-plastiques-comment-ca-marche-149288>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.1787/de747aef-en>

Impacts of different recycling scenarios on global virgin plastic production in the context of various primary plastic production reduction targets (Karali et al. 2024).

Now, consider a scenario where 55% of plastic waste would be recycled by 2030, as advocated by the European Union's Green Deal for plastic packaging¹²—an unrealistic goal on a global scale. According to this hypothesis, the increase in virgin plastic production is delayed by about twenty years compared to historical trends, but its growth continues almost exponentially.

Even a scenario with 90% recycled plastic—which is utopian—would only delay virgin plastic production by seventy years and would not change the fact that it continues to increase.

The most ambitious scenario, proposed by Rwanda and Peru¹³ in the negotiations of the international treaty on plastic pollution, calls for a 40% reduction in virgin plastic production by 2040 compared to the reference year 2025. Even in this case, plastic production in 2040 would still correspond to that of 2010.

None of these trajectories change the fundamental problem: global virgin plastic production has doubled over the past fifteen years, and this trend continues, as anticipated in the Meadows Report in 1972 (Meadows et al., 1972), through the growth of industrial production and its corollary, pollution.

In all cases, plastic recycling has only a minor impact on virgin plastic production. Moreover, these figures are overestimated: they assume that plastics produced and consumed become waste available for recycling in their year of production, without considering the stock of plastics still in use. This is generally true only for packaging, which accounts for about 40% of plastic production.

¹² https://france.representation.ec.europa.eu/informations/pacte-vert-pour-leurope-en-finir-avec-les-dechets-demballages-encourager-la-reutilisation-et-le-2022-11-30_fr

¹³ https://france.representation.ec.europa.eu/informations/pacte-vert-pour-leurope-en-finir-avec-les-dechets-demballages-encourager-la-reutilisation-et-le-2022-11-30_fr

There is urgency, as plastic pollution (Villarrubia-Gómez et al., 2024) contributes to exceeding at least six of the nine planetary boundaries¹⁴.

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¹⁴ <https://theconversation.com/comprendre-la-notion-de-limites-planetaires-145227>